

EXA4MIND

D2.2

Data and Workflow Management Toolbox Alpha Status Report

BADW-LRZ

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Abstract

The EXA4MIND project connects pre-eminent databases and data management systems to supercomputing systems and European Data Spaces as well as the world of FAIR research data. The core purpose of this endeavour is running next-generation Extreme Data workflows, with emphasis on data analytics, Machine Learning / Artificial Intelligence, or classical simulations. This deliverable reports on the *Data and Workflow Management Toolbox* provided for this purpose, building upon the successful LEXIS Platform (delivered by the H2020 project, GA 825532). Furthermore, it illustrates the first workflows run by our application cases at supercomputing centres as a basis for the milestone MS5 First Data-driven Workflows have been Executed using Systems at Supercomputing Centres.

Keywords

Extreme Data; Workflow Control; Data Management; EXA4MIND Toolbox

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Dissemination Levels

PU Public Public, fully open, e.g. website

SEN Sensitive Confidential to EXA4MIND project and Commission Services

Deliverable Types

- R** Document, report (excluding periodic and final reports)
- DEM** Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
- DEC** Websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.
- OTHER** Software, technical diagrams, etc.

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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure
API	Application Programming Interface
AQIS	Advanced Querying and Indexing System
CPU	Central Processing Unit (processor)
CRUD	Create Read Update Delete operations on a data
DAG	Directed Acyclic Graph
DBMS	Database Management System
DDI	Distributed Data Infrastructure
DoA	Description of Action
EDD	Extreme Data Database
ETL	A pipeline with extract, transform and load tasks
GA	Grant Agreement
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit (accelerator)
HPC	High Performance Computing
HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol with SSL
IaaS	Infrastructure as a Service
iRODS	Integrate Rule-Oriented Data System
JWT	JSON Web Token
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LEXIS	Large Scale Executions for Industry and Society - H2020 project
OIDC	OpenID Connect
POSIX	Portable Operating System Interface
REST	Representational State Transfer
S3	Simple Storage Service - object storage / REST API based on AWS standard
SMC	Soil Moisture Content
SSL	Secure Sockets Layer
SQL	Structured Query Language
WP	Work Package
YAML	Yet Another Markup Language

Table of Partners

Short Name	Partner
IT4I@VSB	IT4Innovations at VSB – Technical University of Ostrava (IT4Innovations) https://www.it4i.cz/en
BADW-LRZ	Leibniz Supercomputing Centre (LRZ) of the Bavarian Academy of Sciences and Humanities https://www.lrz.de/english/
METU	Middle East Technical University (METU) https://www.metu.edu.tr/
AUSTRALO	AUSTRALO Interinnov Marketing Lab https://www.australo.org/
EURAXENT	Euraxent https://www.linkedin.com/company/euraxent/
CVUT	Czech Institute of Informatics, Robotics and Cybernetics at the Czech Technical University (CIIRC CTU) https://www.ciirc.cvut.cz/
VALEO	Valeo https://www.valeo.com/en/czech-republic/
TERRAVIEW	Terraview https://www.terraview.co/
ALTRNATIV	Altrnativ https://altrnativ.com/?lang=en
VALEO.AI	Valeo.ai https://www.valeo.com/en/valeo-ai/

Executive Summary

To facilitate next-generation Extreme Data workflows, the EXA4MIND Platform needs proper workflow and data flow management. Such management enables computational workflows with analytics, Artificial Intelligence or simulation core tasks across different specialised systems at supercomputing centres – from GPU-equipped clusters, over classical CPU machines to versatile “cloud-native” infrastructure. In particular, it enables application-case partners who are not used to supercomputing systems to deploy their data-intensive workflows in a user-friendly, but well-controlled and systematic manner.

To this end, Task 2.1 has been foreseen to consolidate the experience and previous open-source systems available to the project partners and to provide workflow management for EXA4MIND – which, in the end, we have been able to base on the LEXIS Platform (developed in the H2020 project LEXIS, GA 825532).

This deliverable reports the results of Task 2.1 up to M12 – the “Data and Workflow Management Toolbox Alpha Status”. It first introduces our basic ideas for the toolbox, including some LEXIS Platform background (Section 1), and then elaborates (Section 2) on the toolbox in terms of workflows, data management and user interfaces/resource management. The envisaged relation of the toolbox to the EXA4MIND Extreme Data Database, and the co-evolution with this toolbox is sketched in Section 3. Finally, we expand somewhat (Section 4) on the first workflow examples from EXA4MIND run at our supercomputing centres (IT4I@VSB, BADW-LRZ), which is the basis for certifying milestone MS5 (M12) and conclude (Section 5).

1 Introduction

In this deliverable, we put forward the fundamentals of the EXA4MIND Data and Workflow Management Toolbox. This toolbox enables next-generation Extreme Data workflows at supercomputing centres, focusing on analytics and computations which involve the EXA4MIND Extreme Data Database (EDD) ecosystem for data. The toolbox builds upon the LEXIS Platform (developed in the H2020 project LEXIS, GA 825532) (LEXIS 2023a) and on activities carried out since the beginning of the EXA4MIND project.

LEXIS Platform is a geographically distributed computational workflow and data management platform, federating the supercomputing centres IT4I@VSB, BADW-LRZ and beyond. It takes advantage of modern industry-standard IT techniques such as a token-based login with a single sign-on to a user-friendly workflow and data portal, and well-established frameworks for orchestration as well as distributed data management. A detailed description of the original LEXIS project concept can be found in (Golasowski et al. 2022; Hachinger et al. 2022; Scionti et al. 2020). In short, it defines mechanisms for orchestrating complex computing workflows across multiple supercomputing centres, including automated data movement. The original implementation uses an orchestrator focused on service topologies and maintaining its lifecycle (YSTIA). Distributed Data Infrastructure (DDI) provides asynchronous data and metadata management which uses storage technologies prevalent in the HPC domain, such as POSIX-based parallel filesystems, iRODS for data movement and transfer protocols like HTTPS and rsync/SFTP. Figure 1 shows the main components which form the LEXIS Platform, and their extension by EXA4MIND.

Figure 1: Existing LEXIS Platform components and extension through EXA4MIND.

Since the beginning of the EXA4MIND project, we identified several areas in which the original concepts must be extended to accommodate the needs of the application cases by performing the initial requirements collection in Deliverable D1.1 (EXA4MIND 2023a) and data flow analysis in Deliverable D2.1 (EXA4MIND 2023b). The first important modification is focusing on a more data-oriented orchestration approach, which can leverage the HPC resources and be efficient enough to scale up to the data volumes expected by the application cases. The next modification was raised because at least two application cases (WP5 and WP6) already use object storage interfaces like S3. Instead of forcing them to overhaul their existing solution to connect to iRODS, EXA4MIND will offer several optimised and adapted data management approaches for the application cases within the EDD.

Another important requirement of the application cases in extreme data handling, which is the core focus of EXA4MIND, is the need to select a complex subset of their data (spatial, temporal, relational, etc.). This requires using indices which are usually implemented by a DBMS with a specialised query interface. EXA4MIND must be capable of handling vast amounts of data for future processing and usage by HPC/AI applications and knowledge extraction. Therefore, the original staging mechanism of the DDI must be extended with the support of various other interfaces like S3 objects, SQL or Lucene queries for inverted index DMBS like ElasticSearch. Figure 1 illustrates this concept by putting these interfaces around a concept of a caching mechanism, which will be required to avoid duplicate movements of large amounts of data (for example, when a dataset with hundreds of TBs of images is used for AI training and must be iteratively extended by a small number of images, which may represent selected edge cases).

With these principles at hand, a platform capable of handling Extreme Data can be built, leveraging existing solutions implemented in the LEXIS Platform and extending them with specialised building blocks coming from a domain-specific environment.

2 Current State of the EXA4MIND Toolbox

In this section, we describe concrete steps taken so far in the development of the EXA4MIND Toolbox, starting from the identification of new components and features being implemented on top of the LEXIS Platform. In three separate subsections, we focus on features for workflow orchestration (Subsection 2.1), data management (Subsection 2.2) and user/project handling (interfaces and resource management) (Subsection 2.3), respectively.

2.1 Workflow Orchestration

Two application cases already have some experience using Apache Airflow (The Apache Software Foundation 2023) as a data-oriented orchestrator solution. We evaluated the possibility of using it as a replacement for the current YSTIA orchestrator used in the LEXIS Platform and found it suitable in terms of extensibility and especially scalability. The Apache Airflow is a solution originally developed by a company, later open-sourced and managed by the Apache Foundation. It allows the orchestration of

complex workflows described as directed acyclic graphs (DAGs) used to transform a dataset.

The interface of Airflow allows the flexible management of individual executions of the workflows (DAG runs) down to the possibility of re-running a certain task from the workflow while following all the subsequent dependencies as visible in Figure 2. Its design is highly modular; the components run as separate processes and communicate using a common SQL database and task broker (Redis Labs 2023). This provides interesting opportunities to scale the system up, as many of the components can be simply run in multiple instances.

Airflow is written in Python and individual tasks executed in the workflows are described by a concept of *Operators*, which are essentially formalised task templates. These operators can have an arbitrary set of parameters and can execute arbitrary code with these parameters. In the context of a Python-centric environment such as the LEXIS Platform, operators can be seen as particular Python classes with defined interfaces. A library of such operators is called *Provider*. Airflow already provides a vast set of providers allowing connection to various DBMS or other services. We used this concept to implement a LEXIS *Provider*, which contains a set of operators which use the LEXIS Platform APIs for distributed data management, HPC job management and AAI functions. We have also extended the built-in Kubernetes operator to provide integration with the LEXIS DDI and Cloud environment. An example of a simple workflow which executes a single HPC job and handles input and output data transfer is visualised in Figure 3.

Airflow workflows are natively described as Python files; however, this method does not allow a true declarative approach to workflow specification. The EXA4MIND application cases would like to define different workflows, which share the same set of tasks (Airflow operators). Therefore, we introduced a concept of declarative workflow definition using structured YAML files based on standards like TOSCA (Brogi,

Figure 2: Airflow UI with LEXIS Provider.

Figure 3: LEXIS Workflow as Airflow DAG.

Soldani, and Wang 2014; OASIS 2023) or CWL (Amstutz et al. 2016). The concept is now being implemented and provides an opportunity to develop a graphical user interface for a drag-and-drop approach to workflow definition.

As a complementary solution to a YAML-based description, we have also implemented the possibility of using a *workflow template*. This is essentially a templated DAG file corresponding to a certain workflow pattern (like the simple HPC workflow described above). The same mechanism can be used to create instances of the data flow patterns identified in Deliverable D2.1 (EXA4MIND 2023b), in cases where the application cases do not need new declarative workflows.

The initial version of the Airflow LEXIS Provider thus builds upon the original concept implemented in the LEXIS project, which uses the workflow to call different asynchronous APIs. This provides us with a solid basis for serving the EXA4MIND application cases with the EXA4MIND Toolbox. The toolbox will use Airflow tasks to construct data-driven workflows. The tasks include the execution of code which transforms the data or performs queries to a DBMS.

2.2 Distributed Data Management

The LEXIS DDI uses federated iRODS (Xu et al. 2017) zones and a custom set of REST APIs with asynchronous workers to facilitate data transfers between locations, meta-data management and more. It integrates with the European collaborative data infrastructure EUDAT (EUDAT CDI 2023d; Lecarpentier et al. 2013); to this end, the EUDAT modules B2SAFE and B2HANDLE (EUDAT CDI 2023c; EUDAT CDI 2023b) are used. A detailed description of the entire solution, including aspects of FAIR (Wilkinson et al.

2016) data and metadata handling, has been given by Munke et al. (2022). During the evaluation of the application case requirements, we identified several possibilities for improving upon the original LEXIS DDI with data management in the context of the EXA4MIND EDD. One area of concern was the slow speed in querying metadata, especially from remote locations, which was due to the overhead of the native iRODS protocol and built-in access policy checks. Another aim we defined has been support for object-based storage (such as S3) or direct querying of DBMS interfaces.

To improve the metadata querying time and prepare the solution for Extreme Data provided by the EXA4MIND application cases, we introduced the concept of a centralised metadata index (based on an inverted index data structure) implemented in ElasticSearch (Elastic 2023). The solution keeps the metadata in both iRODS zones and a centralised ElasticSearch instance. Consistency is enforced by an API responsible for dataset management. Data set query times have improved significantly since then, which has paved the way for data ingestion from the EXA4MIND application cases. The same solution opens the possibility to enforce complex metadata schemes or query metadata for a large number of datasets with the same performance, which would be beneficial for the toolbox.

Additional storage resources are being evaluated now, especially in connection with the concept of a dataset in Airflow and the LEXIS DDI. S3 support is being integrated as an additional interface. The caching mechanism being introduced as EXA4MIND extension of the LEXIS DDI could be also based on an object store which is local to the compute resource used for the analysis (i.e. shares the same data centre); however, strict consistency must be enforced.

2.3 User Interfaces and Resource Management

LEXIS Platform offers a portal as a “one-stop-shop” for platform users, which can be conveniently used within EXA4MIND where fitting. After a single sign-on, it allows for data up- and downloads (for input and output data as well as necessary software to be uploaded), metadata management, and workflow creation and execution. The portal has been continuously updated, and EXA4MIND has helped to upgrade it to introduce additional flexibility in terms of views needed by the application cases. Complementary to this graphical user interface approach, the LEXIS Platform exposes all features through REST APIs. We decided to provide a language-specific Python library (Py4Lexis; cf. LEXIS 2023b) as a wrapper around the APIs to facilitate easy integration of the application cases and their existing code with the EXA4MIND Data and Workflow Management Toolbox.

After signing on to the portal, authentication is managed with OpenIDC JWT tokens throughout workflows (Golasowski et al. 2022). Thus, authentication to the back-end computing and data systems is possible during the workflow without further requests to the user. In this, the LEXIS Platform keeps following a zero-trust approach. Authentication can be delegated to external identity providers. To this end, the OpenIDC provider based on Keycloak (Red Hat 2023) in the LEXIS Platform is federated with two major identity providers – MyAccessID by GÉANT (GÉANT Project and Association 2022) and B2ACCESS by EUDAT (EUDAT CDI 2023a). The possibility of integrating with European identity providers will be crucial for efficiency and usability when connect-

ing the EDD to European Data Spaces, as planned in EXA4MIND. On a practical level, it makes access to EXA4MIND and LEXIS Platform functionalities much smoother, as users may use their own institutional or personal credentials.

3 Development of EXA4MIND EDD and AQIS Features – Integration with the Toolbox

This section provides an outlook beyond M12 on the project, with a focus on the co-evolution of the Data and Workflow Management Toolbox with EDD and the Advanced Query and Indexing System (AQIS) as core EXA4MIND components. EDD shares some technical concepts with the original LEXIS DDI (API/worker architecture), but at the same time introduces a new set of basic principles to facilitate data management. Not only does it feature adaptive strategies to handle Extreme Data (i.e. different data backends from DBMS to different object storage systems), but it also allows for high-performance queries and EDD-wide queries via AQIS.

Subsection 3.1 lays out the envisaged integration concept of EDD, AQIS and the Data and Workflow Management Toolbox. Subsection 3.2 explains which new interfaces are necessary for this integration, for data exchange with European Data Ecosystems and the usage of EDD data on HPC systems.

3.1 EDD: Relation to Data and Workflow Management Toolbox

The EXA4MIND EDD is an ecosystem that extends the LEXIS DDI by adding DBMS support through AQIS and other transfer protocols as backends for data-driven workflows. Essentially, a unified interface for triggering data movements and executing queries is set up between various data management and storage systems (with their different lower-level interfaces) within a single data centre or between multiple geographical locations.

Such unification hides technical differences between different DBMSs and storage systems, which must be handled transparently by EDD. Apart from obvious differences in communication protocols, there are more fundamental problems related to access-control semantics and policy implementations or data organisation. Addressing these differences is one of the fundamental challenges in implementing EDD and its AQIS component.

AQIS encapsulates the different DBMSs and makes them uniformly accessible at least concerning basic CRUD functions (read or write all data, read or write data in a certain time range, etc.). It will be reachable across different systems and sites; data caching can be implemented as part of the workflow to avoid duplicated data transfers.

The architectural vision of the Data and Workflow Management Toolbox based on EDD then focuses on unifying data transfers and various querying interfaces for indices through AQIS by extending the LEXIS Staging API with a new AQIS data source/target.

When this source or target, together with a formalised AQIS query, is given instead of a conventional file system with a directory path, EDD will address AQIS to receive or send the data through the specified query. This is one of the central ideas in EXA4MIND which shall make it possible to facilitate data connectivity between computing clusters, EDD and European Data Spaces.

3.2 EDD Interfaces for Usage, FAIRification, and HPC-based Processing of Data

EXA4MIND features a rich set of preprocessors and adaptors as well as use-case-centric APIs (e.g. for web portals to attach to) to support the application cases in data usage. Extending the interfacing, data exchange mechanisms and FAIRification mechanisms of EDD to interact with European Data Ecosystems will go far beyond what was possible with the LEXIS DDI. In particular, the publication of selected data contained in DBMS will be facilitated, which constitutes a semantic challenge not foreseen in the LEXIS Platform.

Another important part of the EXA4MIND concept and architecture development is integration models for using EDD data in HPC environments. To this end, the usage of DBMS or DBMS data on HPC systems is being investigated in Task 2.3. In principle, HPC codes can interact with DBMS data in three ways: (i) DBMS data are dumped/re-ingested to be used in the form of normal files in the HPC context, (ii) DBMS data are dumped/re-ingested, but on the HPC system they are used via a local DBMS server, started on each computing node, at least for read access, or (iii) a central DBMS server is started on a reserved node in the HPC-system context. These mechanisms are currently being evaluated, and on the BADW-LRZ Linux Cluster HPC system, mechanisms (i) and (ii) seem at least feasible. Further tests have to concentrate on feasibility and performance, to recommend one or more methods for HPC access to DBMS data to WP4, WP5 and WP6.

4 First Data-driven Workflows Executed at Supercomputing Centres

To summarise the concepts from this deliverable, we describe initial workflows from our application cases (WP4-WP6) that will make use of the data and workflow management toolbox. The first test runs of these workflows, e.g. with manual control have already been executed at the supercomputing centres. Clearly – having presented the alpha version of the toolbox here – the task of porting these workflows to use the toolbox will be the next challenge for EXA4MIND. We are confident that tackling this challenge will bring significant benefits in terms of workflow efficiency.

4.1 Scientific Application Case (WP4) Examples

WP4 has become very well acquainted with the supercomputing infrastructure operated by IT4I@VSB, mainly the Karolina cluster. Below, the two deployed and executed workflows are described.

4.1.1 User-defined Analysis

The first workflow models the most basic use case which is user-defined analysis. The workflow performs a series of analyses on a given topology and trajectory file using the Ptraj program (Roe and Cheatham III 2013). The workflow consists of the following steps:

- ◆ The workflow is initiated by running the `run-ptraj_1.sh` shell script. Currently, as no database exists, there are hardcoded paths to the trajectory and topology files, stored in the HPC project directory.
- ◆ The shell script executes the ptraj program with the `ptraj.in` trajectory command file, which contains the commands for the desired analyses.
- ◆ The ptraj program outputs several `.dat` files, which contain the results of the analyses, such as the pucker or chi angle.

The workflow is specific to the input files and does not have any parameters that the user can adjust. The workflow requires the ptraj program to be installed and accessible on the HPC system.

4.1.2 Comparison with Experimental Data

The second workflow performs a comparison of analysis of results with experimental data. As such, this workflow can be chained with the previous one and we do reuse the results of the previous workflow for the comparison. The second workflow consists of the following steps:

- ◆ The workflow is initiated by running the `md-exp-comp.sh` shell script, which takes no input arguments.
- ◆ The shell script performs several operations on the data files generated by the first workflow, such as merging, filtering, calculating, and comparing.
- ◆ The shell script outputs several `.dat` files, which contain the comparison results between the experimental and simulated data, such as NOE, uNOE, J-coupling, and RMSD.

The workflow requires the data files from the first workflow to be present in the same directory.

4.2 Industry Application Case (WP5) Examples

The WP5 workflows are centred around AI workflows using HPC. They consist of both inference and training tasks and are part of a high-level pipeline that should produce ML models trained on private data from VALEO with full traceability. As WP5 deployed its applications on IT4@VSB HPC cluster Karolina, we tested two options for data transfers.

The first one was using the iRODS client on the VALEO side to transfer data to the iRODS zone at IT4I@VSB. As iRODS uses an array of high TCP ports for parallel data transfer, it interferes with network security policies and measures used by VALEO and turned out not feasible. The second option was chunked S3 upload, which is based on HTTPS, therefore using only a single TCP port; at the same time, VALEO already uses it internally for data transfers. Therefore, we used the S3 protocol to transfer the first batch of VALEO data to IT4I@VSB. This corresponds directly with the planned extension of EDD with the S3 support.

The initial workflow executed by VALEO is part of the pre-processing anonymisation process, which performs image segmentation and blurring of sensitive parts like human faces or licence plates. The workflow uses AI models to extract various scene attributes. We successfully developed the first (more coming) AI model that combines object detector and instance segmentation tasks. This AI model creates bounding boxes around objects of 10 different classes (traffic light, traffic sign, person, rider, car, truck, bus, train, motorcycle, bicycle) and marks their presence in images as presented in Figure 4.

The EXA4MIND EDD and AQIS can help in this regard to streamline the image data transfers and especially storing the bounding boxes and instance segmentation data derived by the preprocessing step in specialised databases.

The results of the workflow with the BLIP AI model (Li et al. 2022) used for feature extraction executed on Karolina are as follows. The workflow is roughly divided into three stages – the "BLIP feature extraction", "image loading", and the "JSON file saving". Performed on a single A100 GPU with 40GB of memory.

The input data consumed less than 20GB of the GPU memory (images loaded one by one), and most of the memory was consumed by the BLIP model. During testing, each image was loaded just once and several BLIP feature vectors were extracted. One feature vector for the full image and one feature vector for each Bounding Box (BBox) encapsulating a particular object in the image. The bounding boxes were extracted in advance by the Yolo v8 detection model (Ultralytics 2023). Yolo v8 detection was not part of these measurements, we just used the BBoxes for input. The input data set contains 3,583 images (2MPix each).

4.3 SME Application Cases (WP6) Examples

4.3.1 Agriculture

TERRAVIEW provides two workflows within its **Aquaview** framework: The Soil Moisture Content (SMC) computation workflow and the moisture modelling workflow. Components of these workflows are **currently being shifted to be run at the supercomputing**

Figure 4: Example of Processed Driving scene via WP5 Workflow with Depicted Results of Eetected and Segmented Object Instances (Brightness Enhanced Inside of Polygon) by AI Model.

centres. While usage of LRZ infrastructure – including the Terrabyte satellite-data mirror infrastructure¹ – is also envisaged, first runs will be executed at IT4I@VSB.

TERRAVIEW will use HPC capabilities to accelerate the SMC computation workload. To achieve this, TERRAVIEW will deploy the data ingestion workflow to download the satellite scenes from USGS (U.S. Geological Survey 2023) periodically, to create a cache at IT4I@VSB. Thus, the SMC computation workflow will use this cache to obtain the satellite imagery, rather than locally perform the download using TERRAVIEW’s computational resources. The longer-term aim is here to offload computationally costly and storage-heavy parts of the SMC workflow to supercomputing infrastructure.

For the moisture modelling workflow, Aquaview employs two modelling workflows. The ground models correlate historical weather sequences with satellite Soil Moisture Content maps (SMCMs) and create a virtual moisture probe (model) for each reading pixel. The depth models correlate historical weather sequences with moisture data from probes in vineyards and create a virtual depth moisture probe (model) per the actual physical probe. Both modelling pipelines are data parallel and can run independently. Also, all model training processes within these pipelines are data parallel and can be run in parallel. Historical weather data is stored in files representing virtual weather stations. Historical Soil Moisture Content Maps (SMCMs) are generated

¹Terrabyte satellite-data mirror infrastructure: <https://stac.terrabyte.lrz.de>, https://www.dlr.de/eoc/en/desktopdefault.aspx/tabid-11882/20871_read-84140/

through Aquaview’s site onboarding workflow (DAG).

4.3.2 Healthcare

ALTRNATIV is currently, with the help of WP2, **deploying its ETL worker on the LRZ IaaS-Cloud infrastructure**. This software piece takes charge of the dataflow/workflow preparation and executes different extract-transform-load tasks (pipeline) on datasets. The tasks executed can include data mining or even ML/DL-based inference. Furthermore, ALTRNATIV has prepared a connector to facilitate data management (and later workflow management) in the context of their ETL pipeline with the LEXIS Platform and the Data and Workflow Management Toolbox.

5 Conclusion

In this deliverable, we have laid out how we leverage our experience with the LEXIS Platform to construct the Data and Workflow Management Toolbox for the EXA4MIND Extreme Data workflows.

We have discussed the work performed on the toolbox so far, to provide a baseline for its integration with EXA4MIND EDD and AQIS. In particular, we have described the extensions motivated by an analysis of the EXA4MIND application cases. The concept will be gradually refined and implemented in the next phase, especially as concrete DBMS will be selected and integrated within EDD for the application cases.

To illustrate how the toolbox will be used in the future, the third part of the deliverable has discussed the first workflows run by the application cases on the supercomputing infrastructure. These workflows are also vital for the acceptance of the project milestone MS5. In the project phases to come, EXA4MIND aims to gradually integrate each application case with EDD and AQIS as their features become available.

6 References

- Amstutz, Peter et al. (2016). **Common Workflow Language, v1.0**. DOI: [10.6084/m9.figshare.3115156.v2](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.3115156.v2). URL: <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.3115156.v2>.
- Broggi, Antonio, Jacopo Soldani, and PengWei Wang (2014). “TOSCA in a Nutshell: Promises and Perspectives.” In: **Service-Oriented and Cloud Computing**. Ed. by Massimo Villari, Wolf Zimmermann, and Kung-Kiu Lau. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer, pp. 171–186. ISBN: 978-3-662-44879-3. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-662-44879-3_13](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-44879-3_13).
- Elastic (2023). **Elasticsearch**. <https://www.elastic.co/elasticsearch/>, Cited 01 Dec 2023.
- EUDAT CDI (2023a). **B2ACCESS-EUDAT**. <https://www.eudat.eu/services/b2access>, Cited 30 Nov 2023.
- EUDAT CDI (2023b). **B2HANDLE-EUDAT**. <https://www.eudat.eu/services/b2handle>, Cited 30 Nov 2023.
- EUDAT CDI (2023c). **B2SAFE-EUDAT**. <https://www.eudat.eu/services/b2safe>, Cited 30 Nov 2023.
- EUDAT CDI (2023d). **EUDAT**. <https://www.eudat.eu>, Cited 30 Nov 2023.
- EXA4MIND (2023a). **Deliverable D1.1 Application cases and Architecture Requirements**.
- EXA4MIND (2023b). **Deliverable D2.1 Extreme Data Flow Patterns – Report**.
- GÉANT Project and Association (2022). **MyAccessID Home – MyAccessID – GÉANT federated confluence**. <https://wiki.geant.org/display/MyAccessID/MyAccessID+Home>, Cited 30 Nov 2023.
- Golasowski, Martin and et al. (2022). “The LEXIS Platform for Distributed Workflow Execution and Data Management.” In: **HPC, Big Data, and AI Convergence Towards Exascale**. Boca Raton (FL): CRC Press, pp. 17–35. ISBN: 978-1-003-17666-4. DOI: [10.1201/9781003176664-2](https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003176664-2).
- Hachinger, Stephan et al. (2022). “Leveraging High-Performance Computing and Cloud Computing with Unified Big-Data Workflows: The LEXIS Project.” In: **Technologies and Applications for Big Data Value**. Ed. by Edward Curry et al. Cham: Springer International Publishing, pp. 159–180. ISBN: 978-3-030-78307-5. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-030-78307-5_8](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-78307-5_8). URL: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-78307-5_8.
- Lecarpentier, Damien et al. (2013). “EUDAT: A New Cross-Disciplinary Data Infrastructure for Science.” In: **Int. J. Digit. Curation** 8.1, pp. 279–287.
- LEXIS (2023a). **LEXIS Platform documentation**. <https://docs.lexis.tech/>, Cited 01 Dec 2023.
- LEXIS (2023b). **Py4lexis - Python Client for Lexis Platform**. <https://opencode.it4i.eu/lexis-platform/clients/py4lexis>, Cited 01 Dec 2023.
- Li, Junnan et al. (2022). “BLIP: Bootstrapping Language-Image Pre-training for Unified Vision-Language Understanding and Generation.” In: **CoRR** abs/2201.12086. arXiv: [2201.12086](https://arxiv.org/abs/2201.12086). URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2201.12086>.
- Munke, Johannes et al. (2022). “Data System and Data Management in a Federation of HPC/Cloud Centers.” In: **HPC, Big Data, and AI Convergence Towards Exascale**. Boca Raton (FL): CRC Press, pp. 59–77. ISBN: 978-1-003-17666-4. DOI: [10.1201/9781003176664-4](https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003176664-4).

- OASIS (2023). **OASIS TOSCA**. <https://www.oasis-open.org/committees/tosca/>, Cited 01 Dec 2023.
- Red Hat (2023). **Keycloak**. <https://www.keycloak.org/>.
- Redis Labs (2023). **Redis**. <https://redis.io/>, Cited 01 Dec 2023.
- Roe, Daniel R and Thomas E Cheatham III (2013). “PTRAJ and CPPTRAJ: software for processing and analysis of molecular dynamics trajectory data.” In: **Journal of chemical theory and computation** 9.7, pp. 3084–3095.
- Scionti, Alberto et al. (2020). “HPC, Cloud and Big-Data Convergent Architectures: The LEXIS Approach.” In: **Complex, Intelligent, and Software Intensive Systems**. Ed. by Leonard Barolli, Farookh Khadeer Hussain, and Makoto Ikeda. Cham: Springer International Publishing, pp. 200–212. ISBN: 978-3-030-22354-0. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-030-22354-0_19](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-22354-0_19).
- The Apache Software Foundation (2023). **Apache Airflow**. <https://airflow.apache.org/>, Cited 01 Dec 2023.
- U.S. Geological Survey (2023). **USGS.gov | Science for a changing world**. <https://www.usgs.gov/>, Cited 24 Nov 2023.
- Wilkinson, Mark D. et al. (2016). “The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship.” In: **Scientific data** 3.
- Xu, Hao et al. (2017). **iRODS primer 2: Integrated Rule-Oriented Data System**. Williston, VT: Morgan & Claypool Publishers. DOI: [10.2200/S00760ED1V01Y201702ICR057](https://doi.org/10.2200/S00760ED1V01Y201702ICR057).
- Ultralytics (2023). **Ultralytics YOLOv8**. <https://yolov8.com>, Cited 9 Nov 2023.